

Early Missionary Christianity in China

By Hui-Hung Chen, National Taiwan University

Entry tags: Jesuits; Society of Jesus, Chinese Rites Controversy, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region, Catholic, Roman Catholic, Confucianism, Religious Group

Religious Group-Early Missionary Christianity in China Speaking of Christianity in China, the early missionary period, compared with the later nineteenth century when both the Catholic and Protestant missionaries appeared, is usually defined as from the late sixteenth to the early eighteenth centuries. It was the time when the first most active Christian mission was developed in China. Then, during the European Reformation and overseas expansion, the Catholic missionary was the sole actor in evangelization financed both by the Church and states. The Society of Jesus was officially founded in 1540 and became a significant contributor to the China mission over the centuries. This religious order tied with Asia in the very beginning. Francis Xavier (1506-1552), the first generation of the Jesuits, embarked from Lisbon in 1541 under the auspice of the Portuguese court on behalf of the crown's colony in India. Although Xavier only died on an island outside Macao, not yet set foot on Mainland China, the Padroado, the Portuguese royal supporting system of the Jesuit missionary, became the primary channel to initiate the Catholic missionary history in East Asia. The Italian Jesuit Matteo Ricci (1552-1610) was the most crucial figure in the inception of the Jesuit China mission, who arrived in Macao in 1582. Thenceforth until around 1724, when the Chinese Emperor officially prohibited the religion, this early missionary period of Christianity in China was well-known for its vigorous religious and cultural encounters and thought as the first and most fascinating cultural interaction between Europe and China. The Jesuit evangelization in Japan and China, starting with learning native languages and accommodating cultural elements to their preaching, was proposed by the Jesuit Visitor Alessandro Valignano (1539-1606). Ricci substantially realized this method of accommodation, to fully dress as a Chinese literatus and deeply engage in the Confucian/Mandarin atmosphere. Ricci's most prominent and influential interpretation for the Chinese is to understand Christian God in the original Confucian classics, in which the supreme Shangdi 上帝 or tian 天 (heaven) could be equivalently termed as Catholic Deus. Ricci's return to the Chinese antiquity to conduct his religious adaptation to Chinese culture, standing in conflict with contemporary Neo-Confucianism, was an original way to invent an indigenous comprehension of Christianity. Ricci's argument for early Chinese awareness of the Christian God was to appropriate ancient Chinese terms and imposed on it the Christian meaning of the highest Creator. Although the following controversy after Ricci's death regarding this terminology abandoned them and preferably officiated the Tianzhu 天主, the Lord of Heaven, as the newly coined Chinese term for God, we have considered this "Confucian Christianity" as a highly original hybrid: a monotheist religion and a purist Confucian tradition. It is not merely a result of an ambitious cultural accommodation but also, from the perspective of religious history, one of the most significant characteristic products of the early missionary Christianity in China. The second characteristic of this period could point to another outcome resulting from the intensive and interactive dialogues of the Jesuits and Chinese Mandarins. Tianxue 天學, learning of Heaven, appeared as a new discipline in the intellectual landscape of Late-Ming China. It indicates the Jesuit evangelization through European sciences and knowledge, which were also expected, in the missionary view, to meet Chinese intellectual interests and political needs. The above two characteristics demonstrate the importance of Jesuit accommodation, and also which raised one of the most well-known debates for Christian evangelization during this period, the Chinese Rites Controversy. One of the central controversial issues was the Jesuit interpretation of the Chinese worship of ancestors as the civil and social meanings without conflict with Christian monotheism. Deriving both from the criticisms of other Catholic religious orders, also working in East Asia on a comparatively smaller scale than the Jesuits, and from those doubts inside the Society itself, the Controversy lasted over one century. The Roman Church issued the final rejection of the Jesuit accommodation in 1742.

Date Range: 1580 CE - 1740 CE

Region: Regions of the Catholic China Missions and Churches

Region tags: China, Beijing, Zhejiang, Yangzi River Valley, Yellow River Valley

The primary geographical spread of the Catholic missions and church communities during this period.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Standaert, Nicolas, ed., *Handbook of Christianity in China, Volume: 635-1800* (Leiden: Brill, 2001).
- Source 2: Mungello, David E., *The Great Encounter of China and the West, 1500-1800*, 2nd ed. (Lanham, MD: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers, 2005).
- Source 3: Hsia, R. Po-Chia, *A Jesuit in the Forbidden City: Matteo Ricci 1522-1610* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010).
- Source 1: Brockey, Liam, *Journey to the East: The Jesuit Mission to China, 1579-1724* (Cambridge: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2007).
- Source 2: Spence, Jonathan, *The Memory Palace of Matteo Ricci* (New York, 1984).
- Source 3: Charbonnier, Jean-Pierre, *Christians in China: A.D. 600 to 2000*, trans. M.N.L. Couve de Murville (San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 2007; orig. French edition 2002).

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://referenceworks.brillonline.com/entries/jesuit-historiography-online/the-historiography-of-the-jesuits-in-china-COM_192534
- Source 1 Description: "Jesuit Historiography Online"- The article "The Historiography of the Jesuits in China," by Paul Rule, first published on 2016. One of the most updated review article for the subject.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.bc.edu/content/bc-web/centers/Ricci-Institute/research-tools.html#tab-database>
- Source 1 Description: "The Ricci 21st Century Roundtable on the History of Christianity in China" is administered by the Ricci Institute for Chinese-Western Cultural History, formerly at the University of San Francisco, and moved to Boston College in 2021.
- Source 1 URL: <https://brill.com/search?q3=Jesuits+china>
- Source 1 Description: Many relevant and recent publications and materials on "Brill Open."
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.arts.kuleuven.be/chinese-studies/english/cct>
- Source 1 Description: Highlighted from the website:"The Chinese Christian Texts Database (CCT-Database)" is a research database of primary and secondary sources concerning the cultural contacts between China and Europe in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries (from 1582 to ca. 1840). The

database is multi-lingual in the sense that there are references to documents and publications in a wide variety of ancient and modern Asian and European languages.

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/cathen/13034a.htm>

– Source 1 Description: "Catholic Encyclopedia-Matteo Ricci"

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.bc.edu/bc-web/centers/Ricci-Institute.html>

– Source 1 Description: The Ricci Institute for Chinese-Western Cultural History at Boston College is an internationally renowned research center for the study of Chinese-Western cultural exchange. There are abundant and updated research publications, projects and tools.

– Source 1 URL: <https://jesuitportal.bc.edu>

– Source 1 Description: "The Portal to Jesuit Studies" is a comprehensive and well-maintained database.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: https://jesuitsources.bc.edu/search.php?search_query=China

– Source 1 Description: "Jesuit Sources," online site by Institute of Advanced Jesuit Studies, Boston College, U.S., containing some primary sources.

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.sjweb.info/arsi/japsin.cfm>

– Source 1 Description: The facsimile Chinese books in the JapSin Collection, Archivum Romanum Societatis Iesu (ARSI), Rome. The majority of the books are those written or authored by the Jesuits in China during the early missionary period.

– Source 1 URL: <https://indipetae.bc.edu/elasticsearch/search/index?q=china>

– Source 1 Description: "Digital Indipetae Database," the *indipetae* are letters written by Jesuits to their Superior General to apply for the extra-European missions, usually called the "Indies." Jesuits wrote thousands of *indipetae* from as early as the 1560s until as late as the 1960s. Here the link is searched by the key word "China."

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.sjweb.info/arsi/en/publications/ihsi/monumenta/>

– Source 1 Description: The digitalized format of the Monumenta series (MHSI), published by Archivum Romanum Societatis Iesu (ARSI), including some original sources for the Jesuit missions in India, Japan and China.

– Source 1 URL: https://jesuitonlinebibliography.bc.edu/catalog?utf8=%E2%9C%93&search_field=all_fields&q=china

– Source 1 Description: "Jesuit Online Bibliography," containing some primary sources. Here the link is searched by the key word "China."

– Source 1 URL: https://opac.vatlib.it/mss/search?sm=os&k_v=cina&k_f=0

– Source 1 Description: Jesuit and missionary Chinese books housed in the Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana (BAV), Rome. Here the link is searched by the key word "cina" (Italian). Or, under "Manoscritti-Orientale." See Yu, Dong. *Catalogo delle opere cinesi missionarie della Biblioteca apostolica vaticana* 梵蒂岡圖書館館藏早期傳教士中文文獻目錄 (十六世紀至十八世紀) (Citta del Vaticano: Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, 1996).

– Source 1 URL: <https://archivesetmanuscrits.bnf.fr/pageCollections.html>

– Source 1 Description: Jesuit and missionary Chinese books housed in the Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris. The basic catalogue is Courant, Maurice, ed. *Bibliothèque Nationale* Department des

Manuscripts, Catalogue des Livres Chinois, Corean, Japonais, etc. 3 vols. (Paris, 1902-12; reprinted, Tokyo, 1993). The Bibliotheque uses Courant's numbering. For the subject, see especially nos. 6690-7465.

– Source 1 URL: <http://ricci.bc.edu/index.html>

Notes: The subtitle of the online website "Beyond Ricci" is "Rare Books from the Jesuitica Collection at Boston College, U.S., in which there are several primary books regarding the Jesuits in China digitalized and open to access. As the website states, " it focuses on books that deal with east-west cultural exchange, taking the life of legendary Jesuit missionary Matteo Ricci (1552-1610) as the main starting point."

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group of the early missionary Christianity in China should include the European missionaries and the Chinese, and they could have thought differently for various things. The answers in this entry consider all the people of the two cultures.

Reference: Ronnie Po-chia Hsia. "The Jesuit Encounter with Buddhism in Ming China". Christianity and Cultures: Japan and China in Comparison 1543-1644, edited by M. Antoni J. Üçerler, S. J., pp. 18-43.. Rome: Institutum Historicum Societatis Iesu, 2009..

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Reference: Timothy Brook. The Troubled Empire : China in the Yuan and Ming dynasties. Series: History of Imperial China, 5. Cambridge, Massachusetts : Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2010..

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Tianxue/Xixue (天學/西學) From the perspective of religious history, Tianxue was a Chinese understanding of Jesuit Catholicism. The earliest and conscious employment of this appellation Tianxue (learning or study of Heaven) could come from a compilation of Chinese texts, in which we could define this learning in two parts: Christian doctrines and studies of nature/science. The editor, the Chinese literatus Li Zhi-zao 李之藻 (1571-1630) came from Hangzhou and was supposedly baptized by Ricci in Beijing in 1610. The compilation comprises six volumes entitled Tianxue chuhan 天學初函 (The First Collections of the Tianxue) and is dated 1628. The nature of the Tianxue reflects one of the most prominent evangelical efforts by the early modern Jesuits to achieve Christian conversion through, broadly speaking, western knowledge. The unique case of this effort has been shown in the China mission. The studies of nature/science in the Tianxue chuhan include the first Chinese translation of Euclid's geometry, mathematics, and astronomy. Xixue, Western learning or study, was another term to denote all the learnings introduced by the Jesuits, and the first Chinese treatise on Xixue was listed as the first book the Tianxue chuhan includes. Tianxue and Xixue, the two

appellations were interchangeable, and this study shaped the distinctive feature of Confucian Christianity. Although Confucian Christianity was such a particular legacy of the early missionary Christianity in China, it was only one significant part of the history of Christianity in China. Given the spreading of the Catholic evangelization to local villages, whose missions were also conducted by other missionaries besides the Jesuits, the overall history of the churches in China after the Qing showed more complex relationships with local religions rather than Confucianism and the literati culture.

Reference: Erik Zürcher. "Jesuit Accommodation and the Chinese Cultural Imperative.". (David Mungello E., Ed.), *The Chinese Rites Controversy: Its History and Meaning*.. Nettetal: Steyler Verlag, 1994..

Reference: . Tianxue chuhan 天學初函 (First Book Compilation of the Heavenly Studies). 6 vols.. Taipei: Taiwan xuesheng shuju 台灣學生書局, 1964..

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Gernet's conclusion--a Christian impact in China was logically impossible, has been highly debated. However, the detailed textual analyses in his discussion on the Chinese reactions to Christianity show the complexity of the two cultural encounters.

Reference: Jacques Gernet. *China and the Christian Impact: A Conflict of Cultures* (original in French: *Chine et Christianisme: Action et Réaction*). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1985 (orig. French, Paris, 1982)..

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Here take the examples of two more well-known persecutions, respectively in Nanjing (1616-17) and Beijing (1664-70).

Reference: Adrian Dudink. "Nangong Shudu (1620), Poxie Ji (1640), and Western Reports on the Nanjing Persecution (1616/1617)".

Reference: Eugenio Menegon. "Yang Guanxian's Opposition to Johann Adam Schall: Christianity and Western Science in His Work Budeyi". (Roman Malek, Ed.), *Western Learning and Christianity in China: The Contribution and Impact of Johann Adam Schall von Bell, S.J. (1592-1666)*, vol. 1, pp. 311-337.. Nettetal: Stepler Verl., 1998.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Part of the stories of the Chinese Christians with local non-Christians, Buddhists and Daoists, the violence heard much, can be found in Jesuit annual reports. The reference here is a modern reprint of some Jesuit original reports.

Reference: António de Gouvea. *Carta Ânua da China*. Lisbon: Biblioteca Nacional, 1998..

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: This question is for the Jesuits, and the two books of the reference show how the Jesuits were trained and assigned in the Society.

Reference: Liam Brockey. *Journey to the East: The Jesuit Mission to China, 1579-1724*. Cambridge: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2007..

Reference: Dauril Alden. *The Making of the Enterprise: The Society of Jesus in Portugal, Its Empire, and Beyond*. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1996..

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):
– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:
– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:
– Yes
Notes: The membership of the religious order was required to be sent as a missionary.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:
– Yes
Notes: The religious order would require an education for being a qualified member and missionary.

↳ Assigned by gender:
– Yes
Notes: The Society of Jesus was a male religious order and officially founded in 1540.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:
– Yes
Notes: The majority of the Jesuits and missionaries were usually ordained as a priest when they missionized individually in a foreign land.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:
– Yes [specify]: Missionaries would be evaluated regularly inside by the Society. Personal health was sometimes a factor to decide whether a missionary could remain in a foreign mission.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

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↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: The Jesuits claimed that "the world is our house," and being a missionary was one of the chief vocations of the Society.

Reference: John O'Malley W.. The First Jesuits. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1993.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: For the missionary, answering to this question is positive.

– No

Notes: For the Chinese adherents, it is not a necessary question.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: For the missionary of the religious order, answering to this question is positive. However, it is not necessary for other Jesuits.

– No

Notes: For the Chinese adherents, it is not a necessary question.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: The main characteristic of the early missionary Christianity in China is the cultural accommodation, which is fundamentally opposed to coercion.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: For the missionary, Portuguese Padroado (patronage) was financed by the Portuguese crown. Later the French king Louis XIV sent his own missionary entourage, also supported by the royal court. Chinese Qing court has supported the Jesuit missionaries, to some extent.

Reference: Donald Lach F. , Edwin van Kley J.. Asia in the Making of Europe, vol. III, bk. 4. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1993.

Reference: Donald Lach F.. Asia in the Making of Europe, vol. I, bk. 1. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1965.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: The polity here should refer to not only the Padroado, but also the Roman Catholic Church and the Society. The priests were "supported" by the polity, but not "paid" in the sense of personal salary.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: If the question refers to the Society, both officials would sometimes be overlapped. But if referring to the Portuguese crown and the Church, the former points to political and the latter religious.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Catholic Church has long traditions and regulations for religious observance.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

Notes: Referring to the Roman Catholic Church, this answer would be positive.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This conception would have then resorted to the Roman Catholic Church, which had moral distinction for it.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

- ↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:
 - No
- ↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punished in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Cursed by "high god":
 - Yes
 - ↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other divine punishment:
 - Yes [specify]: Go to the hell, instead of heaven.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 200000

Notes: The estimate is for around 1700, counted as the highest point during this period.

Reference: . Handbook of Christianity in China, Volume One: 635-1800. Leiden: Brill, 2001, pp. 383-85..

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.009

Notes: The Chinese estimated population, around 1710, is referred to the book of the Chinese expert Quan Hansheng 全漢昇, see the reference.

Reference: Hansheng Quan 全漢昇. Mingqing jingjishi yanjiu 明清經濟史研究 (Economic History of the Ming and Qing). Taipei: Linkingbooks, 1987, pp. 51-52.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

Notes: Chinese local communities could have been led by an elder Christian. Due to few European clergy, this local community would be usually considered more like a Christian association led by Chinese people themselves, instead of a parish. Therefore, this local association is hard to be recognized with a hierarchy of a single leader.

Reference: Nicolas Standaert. *The Interweaving of Rituals: Funerals in the Cultural Exchange between China and Europe*. Seattle and London: University of Washington Press, 2008,.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Some hierarchy might have existed, but the community might have not been shown or run by an official hierarchy as much as the polities of the Roman Church and the Society.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: The see of Macao was first founded in 1576. Those of Nanjing and Beijing were followed respectively in 1660 and 1690.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: This single leader can indicate the bishop of Macao, when the see was the only one for all of the China mission, in terms of the organization and administration of the Roman Church.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: In terms of the Roman Church, this kind of council could have existed in the foreign missions when the administrative structure of the clergy was simple and few. The College of Macao, in terms of the Jesuit missions, often played a crucial role in church affairs and local administrations.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: For the Chinese leader in the locals, the answer is no. But the Chinese Christian could have thought missionaries who possessed this quality, as the missionaries could exorcise evils and heal the sick.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

Notes: That the local Chinese leader was chosen or assigned might have varied in different places or occasions. All of the following five questions answered "yes" can explain the possibility.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: Here other leaders can mean the missionaries, who could have chosen the Chinese leader when they were available on site.

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– Yes

Notes: When referring to the Church or the Society as the polities, their leaders could have decided who were sent to locals as missionaries and who could be the leader of the local community.

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural power might have been seen by the Chinese as an important quality of the missionary, who could have been considered a religious leader.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Reference: Nicolas Standaert. "The Bible in Early Seventeenth-Century China". (Irene Eber undefined, Ed.), *Bible in Modern China: The Literary and Intellectual Impact*. Sankt Augustin: Institut Monumenta Serica, 1999.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Notes: However, the catechist, usually the Chinese taking charge of the church business as for the most of time the European priest was absent, might have communicated the doctrine to the ordinary people orally. In foreign missions, the ordinary people could have only known the Scripture by the oral means through the missionaries.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: In terms of Christianity, the following questions are related to the Bible. For Christianity and the Bible, there is only God, no other supernatural beings, to have the official authority and religious power.

↳ Revealed by a high god:
– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:
– Yes

Notes: It can be sometimes said so--some other divine origins in addition to God.

↳ Inspired by high god:
– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:
– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:
– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:
– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:
– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:
– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:
– No

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:
– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Depending on where there can be founded a church. In a mission place, a forming of a parish could not be necessarily surrounded by a physical church.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In terms of China, Macao was in its domain even though the Portuguese claimed to be its colony then. During this period, the Church of St. Paul in Macao could have been then counted as the biggest church building in China. The following questions are answered taking example of Macao's St. Paul's. The original churches in Beijing in the seventeenth century, sanctioned by the emperors, were supposedly in great scale as well. However, there is not much to be known.

Reference: Alan Sweeten Richard. *China's Old Churches: The History, Architecture, and Legacy of Catholic Sacred Structures in Beijing, Tianjin, and Hebei Province*. Leiden: Brill, 2020.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 25.5

Notes: If the size can be measured by the surviving facade of St. Paul's of Macao--the church body was destroyed in 1835, this measurement of the height is the facade's, according to the official information of the government, see the website:<https://www.wh.mo/cn/site/detail/18>

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious

monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Even though the area of St. Paul's in Macao, partly still survived to the present, the actual surroundings in the sixteenth to seventeenth centuries are hard to be traced out the exactitude.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Reference: . Departed, Yet Present, Zhalan: The Oldest Christian Cemetery in Beijing. Macao,1995.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The Chinese Christian or people could have thought the Christian chapels similar to local temples. Or, some earlier cases show that the local communities or missionaries borrowed Buddhist temples.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Reference: . Ignazio e l'arte dei Gesuiti. Milan: Editoriale Jaca Book SpA, 2003..

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

- Yes

Reference: Gauvin Bailey Alexander. Art on the Jesuit Missions in Asia and Latin America 1542-1773. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1999.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

- Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

- No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

- Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

- Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

- No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

- Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

- Yes

↳ Humans:

- Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: There are many symbols and subjects in Christian iconography.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Reference: Ignatius Loyola (1491-1556). *The Spiritual Exercises*. One modern reprint by St. Louis: The Institute of Jesuits Sources (1992)..

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reference: Nicolas Standaert. *The Interweaving of Rituals: Funerals in the Cultural Exchange between China and Europe*. Seattle: University of Washington, 2008.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Hell, opposed to Heaven

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

Notes: Anointing the body is an usual way in Christian traditions.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Personal belongings

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Cross, tablets with the name of the dead.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Reference: Nicolas Standaert. *The Interweaving of Rituals: Funerals in the Cultural Exchange between China and Europe*. Seattle: University of Washington, 2008..

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In Christianity, there are other supernatural beings like angels and saints in sacred realms. Moreover, the cult of the Virgin Mary in missions, such as in China as well as in Latin America, vigorously turned Mary into a goddess, in some way.

Reference: Hui-Hung Chen 陳慧宏. "從耶穌會的羅馬聖母聖像看中國聖母的特質和其世界史脈絡" ("The Characteristics of the Virgin Mary in China and Its World-Historical Context: The Madonna Icon in the Santa Maria Maggiore),".

Reference: Linda Hall B.. *Mary, Mother, and Warrior: The Virgin in Spain and the Americas*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 2004..

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: Like the Virgin Mary, she is chaste--the virtue was highlighted in China
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Granting material needs as prayed by the worshipper. The Chinese Madonna has been regarded to a goddess who could grant child and offer protection as needed.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Reference: Sher-shiueh Li 李爽學. Yishu: Mingmo yesuhui fanyi wenxue lun 譯述：明末耶穌會翻譯文學論 (Transwriting: Translated Literature and Late-Ming Jesuits). Hong Kong: The Chinese University of Hong Kong Press, 2012..

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Showing miracles

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Showing some miracles.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels can be counted as non-humans.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of

sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

- ↳ Sacred object(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: sacred arts and iconography
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Yes [specify]: polygamy
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– Yes

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Grant to Purgatory, instead of Hell.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The European missionary explained the Incarnation of Christ to the Chinese people. Recent research also showed how the Chinese people could have considered Christ as the savior to come--one aspect of Christianity mingled with local religious or cults.

Reference: Barend ter Haar. "The Non-Action Teachings and Christianity: Confusion and Similarities". (J., Philip Clart, Ed.), Chinese and European Perspectives on the Study of Chinese Popular Religions (《中國民間宗教、民間信仰研究之中歐視角》). Taipei: Boyoung Publisher, 2012, pp. 295-328..

Reference: Hui-Hung Chen 陳慧宏. "兩幅耶穌會士的聖母聖像：兼論明末天主教的「宗教」" ("Two Jesuit Madonna Icons: Religious Dimensions of Catholicism in Late-Ming China").

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Coming on specified date:

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Coming has already passed:

– Yes

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Christianity would bring the restoration of Chinese ancient traditions or cultures.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

- ↳ Eschaton at some other time:
 - No

- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes

- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - Yes

- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Yes

 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No

 - ↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - Yes

 - ↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:
 - No

 - ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:
 - No

- ↳ Other survival condition:
 - Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

- Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

- Yes

- ↳ What is the nature of this distinction:
 - Strongly present and highlighted

- ↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
 - Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
 - Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
 - Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
 - Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
 - Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
 - No

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
 - All individuals within society (excepting slaves, aliens)
 - All individuals within society
 - All individuals within contemporary world

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - Yes

- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes

- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes

- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes

- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes

- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes

- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: For the priest and church people. For the ordinary faithful, the answer is "no."

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Yes

Notes: Martyrdom was a virtue in the Roman Church. Or, there is a religiously devout act of self flagellation--imitating Christ.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

↳ Destroyed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– No

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– No

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Carry cross or having it at the house

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The cross-cultural enterprise of the Society of Jesus is likened to an empire.

– A state

Notes: This nature is basically defined by that of the Roman Catholic Church.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patorialism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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